

in the narrow ranges of 1590-1580, 600-580 and 540-525 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$ bondings, respectively. Thus the mixed ligand diamine complexes may be represented by the structure as shown in Fig. 1.

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Formation Constants of the Complexes of 2-Benzofuran Glyoxylaldehyde Dioxime with Some Divalent Metal Ions

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THE formation constants of the complexes of 2-benzofuran glyoxylaldehyde dioxime with Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} have been calculated by pH-metric method at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ ($\mu=0.25 \text{ NaClO}_4$). It has also been shown to form 1 : 2 complexes. The trend in the stability constant values of these metal chelates has been found to be $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$.

A survey of the literature revealed that pH-metric studies of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with 2-benzofuran glyoxylaldehyde dioxime have not so far been described. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make the study of these systems potentiometrically.

Experimental

All the metal perchlorate solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Metal ions other

than UO_2^{2+} were standardized complexometrically by EDTA titrations². UO_2^{2+} was estimated by precipitating with ammonia and weighing it as U_3O_8 after igniting the precipitate in a platinum crucible. The ligand solution was prepared in purified methanol.

Systronics pH-meter standardized against a 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate (AR, BDH) was used for all the pH-measurements. The glass electrode was kept for several days immersed in the methanol before use as recommended by Zeidler³. The following solutions (total volume 20 ml) at $\mu=0.25 \text{ NaClO}_4$ (NaClO_4 prepared in methanol) and temperature $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution (0.1M).

(i) 10.00 ml (0.025M) ligand + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) NaClO_4 + 5.00 ml redistilled water.

(ii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) ligand + 1.00 ml (0.025M) $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ / $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ / $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ / $\text{UO}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) NaClO_4 + 4.00 ml redistilled water.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent methanol water (v/v)*. All the titrations of the ligand with and without the presence of metal solutions were performed according to the method of Calvin and Melchior⁴.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constant (pK) of the ligand was determined by pH-titrations following the method of Bjerrum⁴. It is found out from the formation curve obtained by plotting pH against $\bar{n}\text{H}$ values (where $\bar{n}\text{H}$ = average number of hydrogen ions attached to a ligand ion) as pH, where $\bar{n}\text{H}=0.5$ and comes out to be 10.85.

A comparison of pH titration curves of ligand with and without metal ions indicate that the curves for ligand containing metal ions run much below the curve for ligand. The lowering of the curves for binary systems with respect to ligand takes place from the very beginning of the titration. The analysis of the potentiometric data for these systems also shows that the formation of chelate occurs through successive formation. The horizontal distance between the two titration curves obtained with the solutions (i) and (ii) at any value of pH gives the amount of proton liberated by chelation, i.e., the amount of ligand complexed. This value divided by the total concentration of all metal species in the system gave $\bar{n}$. This may be written as

$$\bar{n} = \frac{C_A - [A]}{C_M}$$

where C_A = total concentration of ligand species

* For correspondence.

present (it is assumed for simplicity of treatment that concentration = activity).

$[A]$ = concentration of free ligand.

C_M = total concentration of all metal species.

The values of $\bar{n}$ were plotted against the corresponding values of pA and the values of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively.

The refined values of $\bar{n}$ were then calculated using Bjerrum's splitting (spreading)⁵ factor X for each corresponding value of A . The final values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ may then be obtained from the plots of pA and $\bar{n}$ (refined) as the values of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values of formation constants are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Metal ion	$t=30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$		
	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log \beta$
Mn^{2+}	5.78	3.10	8.88
Co^{2+}	5.97	3.95	9.92
Ni^{2+}	6.00	4.57	10.57
UO_2^{2+}	6.86	4.84	11.70

A perusal of results shows that formation constants of the complexes are increasing in the order $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. The order of stability follows Irving-William Rule⁶.

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Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2',6'-Diethylaniline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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LITERATURE survey indicates that no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-diethylaniline with bivalent metal ions appears to have been carried out.

In the present communication the dissociation constants of the reagent and successive stability constants of a few of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-diethylaniline was synthesised by dissolving 10 gms of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in absolute ethanol and to this was added equimolar quantity of 2,6-diethylaniline. The mixture was refluxed for about one hour on water bath and then was allowed to cool when solid separated out which was removed by filtration. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get analytically pure compound (observed m.p. 77°).

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. analytical grade except the perchloric acid which was of E. Merck grade.

The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in our earlier recent communication².

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The reagent formation curve extends over a range $0.39 < \bar{n}_A < 1.55$ and is wavelike indicating the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L in steps, separable. The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were determined from half integral points at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

The metal-ligand stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for the metal ions studied were determined